

FORMING AND DEVELOPING TECHNOLOGIES OF CRITICAL THINKING

Nuriddinova Mastura Ikramjon qizi

Student of state of institut of Foreign Language

Gmail: nuriddinovamastura6@gmail.com

Scientific supervisor: **Zubaydova Nilufar Negmatullayevna**

Annotation: Today, critical thinking covers almost all fields, including education and professional development. For example, in Uzbekistan, young elementary school students who enter the presidential school also take a critical thinking test. In addition, questions about critical thinking are asked in the entrance exams for higher education, that facts are given to students or pupils requires that he/she needs to think about the data. Methodological guidelines for the formation of critical thinking and developing technologies are discussed on the following pages.

Key words: developing methods, Khan Academy, Coursera, platforms, Reddit Quora, Stack Exchange, games, Minecraft education Edition, SimCity, Kerbal Space Program, intelligence programs, ChatGPT, Socratic,IMB Watson,online books and articles, analyze ideas, self-evaluation, facts, think logically, critical thinking

INTRODUCTION

Critical thinking is a special type of thinking that is concluded by analyzing facts. Developing critical thinking involves developing people's ability to solve problems effectively analyze and approach them logically by developing complex thinking skills. In addition technologies help to develop in this ways. Technologies that develop critical thinking are of great importance. Nowadays it covers in the fields of professional development as well as education.

There are a lot of methods developing critical thinking skills. Critical thinking is developing a lot among today's youth. The main reason for this is that critical thinking skills are being used in the current education system and professional development. As an example, current elementary school students in Uzbekistan are solving critical thinking issues when taking exams for presidential schools. In addition, the fact that critical thinking questions are asked in higher education entrance exams requires students and students to have sufficient information in this regard. There are several ways to develop critical thinking. For example, people

should first develop the ability to ask questions. It is no exaggeration to say that questioning is the main part of critical thinking. When studying a topic in depth, you should ask yourself the question “How?” “Why?” these questions will help you understand the topic more clearly. If we look at the next method, analyzing ideas or finding their logical connections, analyzing problems, studying different sources, identifying similarities and differences in them forms this skill. Being open to different views and them also strengthens critical thinking. Solving any problem in several ways action develops critical thinking. We can see the importance of critical thinking in helping young people to find solutions to problems. If the ideas are clearly and logically based and used with evidence and facts, then the level of critical thinking is high. The ability to think will improve. Evaluate pros and cons sides. It is important to find pros and cons sides any situations and problems. After, you analyze them bu critical thinking in this way. Evaluate pros and cons sides will make it easier to find solution to problem.

The process of critical thinking takes time and practice, but these skills will develop your critical thinking by regularly practice and use these methods. Also technologies plays a essential role to develop critical thinking. Also they help to improve critical thinking. Nowadays Many people are using technologies and they are very developing rapidly.

For example. There are a great of platforms and programs. Platforms like Khan Academy, Coursera and edX offer courses and exercises. Through these platforms students learn to solve problems indepently, give questions and analyze them. Online discussion platforms and forums.

They are Reddit, Quora, Stack Exchange. They serve as exchanging opinions. These forums help to learn and and analyze other’s perspectives. Games like Minecraft Education Edition, SimCity, Kerbal Space Program are ideal for developing critical thinking. Students can develop to solve problems thinking strategic and creativity’s ability.

Programms developed on the basis of artificial intelligence. These programs such as ChatGPT, Socratic or IBM Watson help to think critically in this process. Through these programs, students learn to give question clearly and analyze deeply. Argumentation mapping tools teach how to understand to analyze. Collections of online books and articles. Scholarly resouces such as Google Scholar, JSTOK and ResearchGate provide students and faculty with acess to scholarly articles and research also helps to improve. Critical thinking can be effective and it will be efficient for all people through these technologies.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the formation of critical thinking and its development helps a person to grow educationally and to prove problems and information with his own opinion, to solve problems effectively and to find solutions to them. At the same time, the formation and development of critical thinking, its continuous practice, and the use of modern technologies and platforms for the development of critical thinking are the most effective ways to achieve this goal. And in this way, a person can find and analyze the causes, problems and solutions of any topic

REFERENCE

1. Azamovna P. F., Mamatovna Y. A. The role of information technology in the development of students' critical thinking //Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research. – 2024. – T. 11. – №. 05. – C. 416-417.
2. U. Y Kuziev, The issue of classification and description of complex structural compounds in uzbek language, Int J Eval & Res Educ 99 (4), 309-314, 2023
3. U. M Azamatovna, Comparative-typological analysis of the terms of folk art, International Journal on Integrated Education 3 (12), 155-157, 2020.
4. N. Dedamirzayeva, U Kuziyev, Teaching English to young learners through games, Oriental Art and Culture, 86-88, 2020
5. U. M Azamatovna, The History Of The Development Of The Terms Of Literary Studies Of The Turkic Peoples.
6. U Qo'ziyev, Tilda soflik masalasi, ta'limda turkiy xalqlar milliy mentalitetini mustahkamlashning dolzarb ..., 2022